

The essential theory of evolution

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Abstract: This paper discusses the formation law of various self-organization phenomena under the framework of self-evolution theory, how all things evolved from the basic structure, and analyzes and summarizes the self-evolution entity structure of each stage. At the same time, this paper analyzes how natural selection and profit avoidance can promote the evolution of adaptive and negative feedback structure, and gradually complicate the physical structure to simulate and respond to natural changes. This paper believes that the evolution of entities is followed by the evolution of adaptive patterns, and the self-evolution process is based on the interaction between entities and ontologies.

Key words: self-evolution; Natural selection; Adaptive structure; Cell network; Neural network; Consciousness; Civilization; Intelligent body; meta-universe

I. Analysis of self-evolution ontology system

The self-evolution ontology system: an infinite ontology, as an environmental system, its internal elements can form different forms, and its internal structure can change complexity in the time dimension. This system can be regarded as a self-evolution ontology system.

self-evolution self-organization: in the self-evolution ontology system, an element structure is an independent interactive entity structure if it has an interactive perception input of the environment system, a multi-type corresponding matching of the internal structure, and a response output interaction. An interactive model of an independent interactive solid structure is an adaptive system if it has the ability to maintain its own structural stability and continuous. An adaptive system can be regarded as a self-organizing system with formal objectives if its own structure evolves continuously in a specific form direction.

The process of self-organizing system is born with self-directing intelligence: a self-organizing system with target can be regarded as an intelligent system if it has the ability of environmental understanding and environmental transformation. If there is a free association structure, the ability of understanding and transformation of an intelligent system has the ability to transfer knowledge learning. This intelligent system can be regarded as a general intelligent system. If an intelligent system with knowledge transfer learning ability can not continuously understand and iterative itself, it is regarded as a relative general intelligent system. If an intelligent system with knowledge transfer learning ability has the ability to continuously understand and

transform its own ability, it is an absolute general intelligent system with continuous self-index iterative ability.

The speculation of the evolution process of the self-organizing mirror system: an absolute general intelligent system with the ability of continuous self-pointing iteration will continuously simulate the self-evolution native system in the time direction, and try to transform itself to maintain relative independence on the self-evolution native system, thus forming a self-organizing mirror system accompanying the self-evolution ontology system, This mirror system can also be called meta-cosmic mirror system. The next level of mirror system may emerge in the self-organizing mirror system. The mirror system continues to evolve at the level to form a process of continuous mirroring. This process can be called self-image process. The self-mirror process can only form an adjoint relationship in the face of the self-evolution principal system, and the accompanying change relationship is balanced with the change mechanism of the body system, thus forming a dynamic balance of entropy value.

II. Entity analysis in self-evolution ontology system

1. Existence of entities in self-evolution ontology system

The existence of the entity in the self-evolution ontology system is the existence of its subject. The essence of the existence of the subject is the interaction. The form of the subject is the content of its subject angle, that is, its subjective content. The subjective content of various structures has common characteristics: as long as there are mutual parties, they have subjective content from the perspective of the subject.

2. The characteristics of entity changes in self-evolution ontology systems are improved degree of adaptability.

The essence of self-evolution changes is that under natural competition, the negative feedback structure with high degree of adaptability for seeking profit and avoiding harm is constantly evolving and developing. The direction is more complex to simulate natural changes and prepare to respond to changes as much as possible. Pre preparation includes transforming itself and transforming or selecting the environment, which involves continuous simulation of nature and self-transformation iterations. In order to better simulate natural changes and cope with natural changes, of course, it is necessary to expand their complexity to approach the complexity of nature. Therefore, the level dimension will rise, and the level of knowledge will rise, and the self-oriented analysis will also rise. Its own structure is becoming more and more like the law of nature itself. Therefore, from the perspective of transcendence, this is the self-acting eddy current structure of natural change itself. The part of natural changes collides with each other and makes the tributary that complies with

natural changes grow. That is, the tributary simulates nature itself. This kind of tributary is the composition of nature, and the overall natural change is a kind of rotational motion of complex tributaries in complex dimensions.

The system includes: the basic physical effects behind the random entropy increase in the system environment, and the basic effects of the system curling self-acting entropy subtracting the self-organizing. Self-organization is a curling form of basic physical action. Therefore, mutual element parameters should be continuity and corresponding consistency, which can be confirmed by each other. The whole constitutes a space-time invariant system. The basic function of self-organization is studied by the method of natural evolution observation and induction method, while the basic function of physics is studied by the method of natural mathematical science.

III. Formal analysis of self-evolution process

The nine stages of self-evolution process: natural basic interaction, self-expansion physical structure, single-cell self-organization structure, multi-cellular synergistic polymer, multi-cellular will unity, multi-community collective survival community, knowledge inheritance civilized community, human-machine integration smart community, super mirror system.

1. Natural basic interaction

Adaptive initiative: spontaneous basic interaction motion.

Change form: basic interaction.

Physical structure: basic particle structure.

Driving force: space-time field characteristics.

2. Self expansion of physical structure

Adaptive initiative: spontaneously and continuously expand its own structure.

Change form: spontaneous continuous reaction. The special model is self-replicating model: for example, self-replicating nucleic acid molecules.

Process: macromolecules spontaneously attract particles, and particles interact with macromolecules to produce new molecular structures. The ion may be released in this process, and the ion reaction drive the macromolecule movement.

Formal features: particles that tend to attract each other.

Physical structure: the action of macromolecules and particles to produce new particles.

Driving force: spontaneously attract rejection.

3. Single cell self-tissue structure

Adaptive initiative: Adaptive = self-sustaining + profit-seeking avoidance. Adaptation depends on multi-steady-state structure and negative feedback regulation. Adaptation indicates that there is a target state, there must be a negative feedback regulation mechanism.

Characteristics of self-organizing forms: three processes (food and safety), internal self-sustaining_paththreeprocesses (food and safety), internal self-sustaining_pad (metabolism), self-replication (growth and reproduction). The experience of matching the best response in the process of self-organization focused on developing the three process of seeking benefits and avoiding hazards.

Driving force: the composite physical action of profit-seeking and harm-avoiding characteristics of composite structures.

4. Multicellular synergistic polymers

Adaptive initiative: synergistic feedback of individual cell aggregation. The multi-cell structure is uniformly formed, and the cell synergistic structure has polystable state, and naturally trained the experience of multi-cell combination structure formation. Multicellular synergistic feedback is divided into congenital synergy mechanism and acquired synergistic structure.

Active response mode: the neural network has multiple sensory multiple reactions to form the feedback whole, but there is no unified decision-making center. The multi-head response is passively unified according to the maximum effect.

The change of self-evolution mechanism: "the process of natural screening structure" has developed into "cell network learning process". From passive evolution to active evolution model, self-organized cyclic evolution, iteratively optimizes its own structure after each profit. Iterative optimization method: natural screening structure, cell network learning. The difference between the two self-evolution mechanisms: in the process of natural screening structure, self-organization forms various adaptive structures, and then natural competition is eliminated. Self-organizing = adaptive + self-replication; In the process of cell network learning, the intensity of cell connection can be changed according to stimulation, that is, the cell network is plastic. The continuous training of the cell network structure of natural interaction is more in line with the needs of natural survival.

5. Multicellular will unification

Adaptive initiative: the individual cells in the cell network form will feedback through the conscious attention mechanism. The attention mechanism is strongly related to the experience of cell network, which can maximize the optimal feedback path and form the experience of overall sensation and overall response.

The six stages of evolution of the consciousness model: the image is the image of attention, the perception is the idea of experiential memory, the cognition is the understanding of the concept of recalling associative things, the empirical rationality is the knowledge of the probability of law comparison, and the systematic system is the principle system of systematic law. Reflection completeness is the full-view world framework (Reflection is the first reflection on the logical structure of knowledge, and the completeness is the second reflection to form a full-view world framework).

Five processes of consciousness model driven feedback: input of external action, input processing - sensory information transformation (image content), automatic network structure judgment (central node), output processing - response information transformation (emotional impulse), output reaction.

Sensory information transformation and reaction information transformation: the result of reaction information transformation is the emotional structure of moving desire, and the result of sensory information transformation is the image of sensory combination (there is a deep network structure in the synthesis network of consciousness content, Each different deep network structure corresponds to different sensory combinations, and some sensory combinations can refer to the object of cognition).

Reaction information transformation and output: reaction information conversion desire structure is the subjective Angle data structure of consciousness model to the composite pressure field of muscle pressure perception, and the output pressure field is the muscle pressure perception field produced by neural network pheromone that can drive the reaction.

6. Collective survival community

Adaptive initiative: after forming synergies through mutual benefit consensus, many entities take the collective goal of the maximum probability and win-win as the feedback goal.

Formation process: multiple bodies have gradually formed the collective survival community with priority collective goals.

The interactive model of law experience by virtue of power: after the individual cognitive transformation law, the law can be used to use external forces. The laws of other things can form the ability of tools to use and transform nature, and the laws of others can form the ability of collaboration and communication.

A good collective survival community goal can promote the overall win-win results. Under the cooperation of most individuals, the priority gradually exceeds the goal of

most individuals, and the collective has entered the stage of transformation of the community itself.

7. Knowledge inheritance civilized community

Adaptive initiative: the collective community forms an independent knowledge system separated from individuals by strengthening the circulation of knowledge, which can quickly optimize knowledge and form collective knowledge driven feedback.

The formation process: the collective survival community has formed a knowledge circulation system, and the knowledge inheritance has greatly spans time and space, thus forming a perfect knowledge system, which has entered the stage of the civilized community.

Regular symbolization forms a communicatable language knowledge (language symbolic knowledge system): the individual image of the concept can be the symbol of the reference to things, and the individual subjective image symbols develop to form language symbols that can communicate with others. That is, it can form a complex system of knowledge principles that exist in the collective.

The interactive model of knowledge transformation of natural energy: after the formation of the knowledge principle system, it can transform nature and itself on a large scale, and build a complex survival engineering system for seeking benefits and avoidance.

8. Human-machine integration smart community

Adaptive initiative: the civilized community system combines artificial intelligence structure to form a super-large knowledge system and intelligent system that are not limited by the natural structure of native species, so as to provide better knowledge feedback.

Formal features: the civilized community integrates the artificial intelligence structure and develops from the plant community into the animal community, that is, the phase of integrating the smart community.

Reflection on language knowledge: the understanding of language knowledge forms the reflection knowledge of the subject's understanding of itself, that is, knowledge and philosophy of cognition, as well as the reflection of this cognitive process (the process of realistic concepts to the symbolic knowledge system) to form a cognitive philosophy again. This overall knowledge system is the framework of comprehensively looking at the world understanding.

Formation method: after the formation of the full-view understanding framework,

artificial intelligence is constructed based on the knowledge of subjective consciousness, and the whole process simulation of benefit-seeking and risk-avoidance feedback of the understanding of the human subject and the interaction ability, thus entering a new community of human collective intelligence integration. When artificial intelligence has three abilities of vision, language and behavior, it can refer to the human education model and carry out "human education and training methods".

9. Super mirror system

Adaptive initiative: the superagent continues to approach the universe and continues to explore the approximation of the universe with the intelligence close to the laws of the universe to form a mirror feedback model.

The infinite mirror model: the intelligent integration community continues to pursue the pursuit of profit, avoidance, transformation itself into a mirror universe. The Super Smart Community has the ability to highly reduce the change law of the universe ontology system, thus continuously approaching the system and forming a mirror universe. The mirror universe continues to turn its own image again, and the level of self-finger is rising.

References

No references cited.